

SITE	YEAR	AREA	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT
GPR	2010	B		Min: 62.4852 Max: 63.138	1229 ☐ Natural ☒ Anthropic

In cross-section? Yes No In elevation drawing? Yes No Photos: Yes No #: 779-782 Photo Model: Yes No #:

DEFINITION: cut in 1173 - starting pt for channel (1228) Covered by SU: 7165 Fills SU: Filled by SU: 1177, 1199, 1203

HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? Color Composition Compaction FORMATION PROCESS: Accumulation Construction Cutting Erosion Collapse Intentional deposition

INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are			SOIL/MATRIX
Anthropic	Geological	Organic	clay ___% silt ___% sand ___%
☐ Pottery ☐ Nails ☐ Tiles ☐ Marble ☐ Amphorae ☐ Quarried debris ☐ Dolia ☐ Slag ☐ Brick ☐ Mosaic tile(s) ☐ Basalt slabs ☐ Mortar ☐ Opus signinum ☐ Coins ☐ Painted plaster ☐ Metal (specify) ☐ Burnt Adobe ☐ Collapse debris ☐ Other (specify) ☐ Glass	☐ Tufo (specify) ☐ Travertine ☐ Other Limestone ☐ Basalt ☐ Clay ☐ Sand ☐ Silt ☐ Pebbles (range) ☐ Gravel (range)	☐ Charcoal ☐ Ash ☐ Animal bones ☐ Human bones ☐ Animal teeth ☐ Human teeth ☐ Shells ☐ Other (specify)	☐ Granular ☐ Layered ☐ Cohesive
			Compaction Color
			☐ Hard ☐ Black ☐ Brown ☐ Compact ☐ Gray ☐ Light Brown ☐ Friable ☐ Light Gray ☐ White ☐ Loose ☐ Yellow ☐ Red ☐ Soft ☐ Light Yellow ☐ Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)

Northern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit Depth: Original Not Original

Southern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Western Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

Eastern Limit Original Not Original Excavation Limit

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE

Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts:
Is covered by: 1165, 1384	Covers: 1001 (bedrock)
Is cut by:	Cuts: 1173 (tufo floor)
Is filled by: 1177, 1199, 1203	Fills:

OBSERVATIONS: Excavated w/ pickaxe & shovel (used trowels to define rocks and other features) for 3 days. Rained on afternoon of 1st day. Otherwise hot & sunny.

DESCRIPTION

Position within sector: Southwestern section, e.g. southwestern part of Trench B

Shape: Oblong & cut (in half?) by Southern excavation limit
yep

For layers complete this section:

Surface (slope direction: visible inclusions):

Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope)

Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?):

Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commigled other (specify)

<p>For cuts complete this section:</p> <p>Cut edges: ☒ rounded ☐ straight</p> <p>Cut sides: ☐ straight ☒ concave ☐ convex ☐ sloping</p> <p>Cut bottom: ☐ flat ☐ concave ☒ irregular</p> <p>How is cut top edge? ☐ sharp ☒ rounded</p> <p>How is cut bottom edge? ☐ sharp ☒ rounded</p> <p>Observations: cut into tufo floor & everything below it (prep layers) exposes the bedrock (1001) but doesn't cut it</p>	<p>Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North):</p>
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→ see back for extended sketch from 2d1 excavation

GPR 11 — rescan SV sheet (back) and overlay ✓

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

INTERPRETATION

The courtyard with its tufo floor was there and it was cut into in order to reach the bedrock and begin construction on the channel (1228), or cut was dug in order to use some precious building material.

Excavation of cut 1229 continued + completed in 2011-SJL

<p>SOIL SAMPLING: ☐ Yes ☒ No Total volume of layer (buckets): Sample quantity (buckets): Sample fraction (%):</p>	<p>NON SOIL SAMPLES: ☐ Yes ☒ No If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.): Size:</p>	<p>SIEVING: ☐ Yes ☒ No Total volume of layer (buckets): Sample quantity (buckets): Sample fraction (%):</p>
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<p>STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY ☒ Good ☐ Fair ☐ Poor</p>	<p>Filled-out by <u>CAK</u> Revised by <u>CMH</u> PDFd by <u>JJM, AMS</u> Entered by</p>	<p>on <u>23-7-10</u> on <u>23-7-10 / 29/7/2011</u> on <u>27.07.2010, 21/7/11</u> on</p>
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